
The Joint Influence of Learning Platforms and Gender on Students' Academic Performance in Algebra in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

Dr. WELI Bumia

bumswel@gmail.com

Department of Educational Technology,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State

&

Dr. GEO-WOSU Charity

charitygeowosu2017@gmail.com

Department of Educational Technology,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State

Abstract

This study investigated the effect of Gamified Quizizz and Google Classroom Platforms on students' performance of Algebra concepts in Private Junior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Three objectives and three research questions were answered, and three corresponding hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised two million, one hundred and ninety-eight thousand, four hundred and forty-three Junior Secondary School III Mathematics students in 743 fully accredited private junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The sample size of the study comprised 251 Junior Secondary School III Mathematics students drawn from intact classes in selected private junior secondary schools. The multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted to select the sample for this study. The instrument used for data collection was Algebra Performance. The instrument was validated by three experts. The reliability of the instruments was determined using PPMC, which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.92. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that a significant difference exists among students taught using Gamified Quizizz Platform, those taught using Google Classroom Platform and those taught using Face-to-Face Method in their academic performance and retention of Algebra concepts. The study concluded that the integration of Gamified Quizizz and Google Classroom platforms significantly enhanced students' performance in Algebra concepts compared to the traditional Face-to-Face method. The study recommended, among others, that mathematics teachers should adopt gamified teaching strategies and learning to enhance students' academic performance and retention of Algebra concepts.

Keywords: Learning platforms, gender, academic performance, algebra, students, Port Harcourt.

Introduction

Mathematics is a unique discipline that promotes and facilitates critical thinking among its learners. It has been at the core of ancient civilisations, dating back to the Greek and Roman empires. Today, Mathematics is equally valued and continues to form the foundation for many other disciplines. Ernest (2015) asserted that Mathematics is instrumental in developing intellect and fostering consistency of thoughts and ideas. Mathematics is essential to the growth of the social, economic, and technological systems of the country. In Nigeria, Mathematics is taught as one of the core topics, especially in secondary schools. In Nigerian secondary schools, Mathematics is a required subject (Ogunode, 2020).

The Comparative Education Study and Adaptation Centre (CESAC), stated that the objectives of secondary school Mathematics are to foster the following: the development of computational skills, the desire and capacity to be precise to a degree relevant to the problem at hand, the development of precise, logical, and abstract thinking, the capacity to recognize problems and solve them using relevant Mathematics knowledge, and the stimulation and encouragement of creativity, originality, and curiosity. In Nigeria's educational system, Mathematics is one of the prerequisites for entry into postsecondary institutions and influences students' decisions about their future careers in science and technology (Oginni et al, 2021). All facets of human life are impacted by Mathematics. Numbers play a central role in all facets of human existence, including social, economic, political, geographic, scientific, and technological dimensions.

Mathematics continues to be a crucial tool that equips people for effective employment, regardless of the profession they are in or their career path (Dele-Ajayi et al., 2019). Understanding Mathematics is essential for daily life and long-term planning, not simply for one's career or the advancement of the country. The mind's creative and cognitive capacities can be enhanced by Mathematics study, and its influence on national development is equally substantial (Etuk & Bello, 2016). However, the scientific character of Mathematics has contributed to gender stereotypes in the field. One such element that has been shown to have a significant impact on students' academic performances, particularly in science disciplines, is gender (Adigun et al, 2015).

In referencing Mathematics skills, Ernest further posited that these attributes lay the foundation for learners to develop the necessary aptitudes to engage and make sense of the world around them. Ernest (2015) also concurred that Mathematics provides a method for correspondence that is current, concise, and unequivocal. Ayllón, Gómez, and Ballesta-Claver (2016) as well as Leikin and Pitta-Pantazi (2013) asserted Mathematics helps to stimulate inventiveness and creative ability in the teaching-learning process. This inventiveness and creative ability extend to learners engaging in meaningful learning construction and problem-solving (Ayllón et al., 2016; Leikin & Pitta-Pantazi, 2013). Gafoor and Kurukkan (2015) posited that everybody needs numerical ideas to assume a mindful part in an equitable society.

Mathematics learning is of utmost importance for students at the elementary and secondary school levels. Chen, Liao, and Chang (2015) asserted that Mathematics is a phenomenon that humankind has used directly or indirectly since ancient times. From the simplest of daily life situations to the most complicated problems, solutions have always been found. Chen, Liao, and Chang (2015) maintained that in the Mathematics curriculum, it is deemed important to train individuals so that they can use Mathematics in daily life, resolve problems, share their solutions and thoughts, participate in teamwork, be confident in Mathematics, and develop a positive attitude toward Mathematics.

However, the learning of mathematical concepts presents numerous difficulties for many students. Romero (2014) suggested that Mathematics is often perceived as a challenging and boring subject for students to grasp. Many have associated this perception of Mathematics being boring with traditional methods of teaching, which are also perceived as being ineffective (Dicheva, Dichev, Agre, & Angelova, 2015). Jayasinghe and Dharmaratne (2013) suggested that traditional methods of teaching are no longer beneficial to students, as they do not facilitate critical thinking in students and also believed that traditional teaching methods allow students to concentrate on exams rather than allowing students to garner a deeper understanding of the concepts being taught.

Statement of the Problem

Mathematics holds a vital position in Nigeria's educational curriculum, remaining a compulsory subject from primary to secondary school. Despite this, students' performance in mathematics remains poor, with many failing or earning low scores, often passing with grace marks. Those pursuing science-related studies face significant difficulties due to their inadequate mathematical foundation. The philosophy of mathematics is currently at a crossroads. Traditional mathematicians view it as the cornerstone of science, while an emerging group of cognitive psychologists, linguists, neurobiologists, and some mathematicians argue that mathematics is a function of the brain. Compounding this issue, many teachers lack adequate mathematical expertise and adhere to outdated teaching methods, relying on textbooks and inherited practices. Consequently, students often develop anxiety toward mathematics, leading to disinterest, even among academically gifted individuals who avoid selecting it as a compulsory subject. Teaching and learning mathematics remain persistent challenges, with various underlying causes. Research in this field is comparatively insufficient, despite mathematics being fundamental to scientific disciplines. It is against this backdrop, this study aimed to explore the effect of Gamified Quizizz and Google Classroom Platforms on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts within the Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study was aimed at investigating the joint effect of learning platforms (Gamified Quizizz and Google Classroom Platforms) and gender on students' academic performance in Private Junior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The objectives of the study were to:

1. Investigate the effect of learning platforms (GQP, GCP, FFM) on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts.
2. Determine the influence of gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts.
3. Determine the joint effect of learning platform (GQP, GCP, FFM) and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts

Research Questions

The following understated research questions guided this study.

1. What difference exists among students taught using Gamified Quizizz Platform (GQP), Google Classroom Platform (GCP) and Face-to-Face Method (FFM) in their academic performance in Algebra concepts?
2. What difference exists between the academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts?
3. What is the joint effect of learning platform (GQP, GCP and FFM) and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide this study.

1. No significant difference exists among students taught using GQP, students taught using GCP and students taught using FFM in students' academic performance in Algebra concepts.
2. No significant difference exists between the academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts.
3. There is no significant joint effect of learning platform and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts

Research Design

The study employed a quasi-experimental non-randomised non-equivalent control group, pre-test-post-test design. This design was most appropriate for the study as randomisation of the students into experimental and control groups was not very possible in the present situation.

The design is schematically represented as follows;

S/N	Groups	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-test
1	Experimental 1(GQP)	O ₁	X ₁	O ₂
2	Experimental ----- (GCP)	2 O ₁	X ₂	O ₂
3	Control (FFM)	O ₁	X ₀	O ₂

Where,

O₁ = Pre-test for all the groups

X₁ = Instruction with Gamified Quizizz Platform (GQP)

X₂ = Instruction with Google Classroom Platform (GCP)

X₀ = Instruction with face-to-face method

(----) = Intact class.

O₂ = Post-test for all the groups

Population, Sample and Sampling Techniques

The population for this study comprised two million, one hundred ninety-eight thousand, four hundred forty-three (2,198,443) Junior Secondary School III Mathematics students (JSS III) in 743 fully accredited private junior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The sample for this study consisted of 251 Junior Secondary School III (JSS III) Mathematics students, drawn from intact classes in three selected private junior secondary schools in the Port Harcourt Metropolis. This sample comprised 83 students (50 males and 33 females) for experimental group I, 86 students (46 males and 40 females) for experimental group II and 82 students (42 males and 40 females) for the control group. This sample was arrived at by using all the JSS III Mathematics students from the three private junior secondary schools selected for this study. Specifically, there were 138 male and 113 female students. The multi-stage sampling procedure was used to obtain the sample for this study, as more than one sampling technique was adopted at various stages of selection.

Research Instrument

The Algebra Performance Test (APT) was used for data collection. The Algebra Performance Test (APT) consisted of 50 multiple-choice test items on Mathematics topics (Simplification

of Algebraic Expressions, Simple Equations and Variations). Each test item had four options (A, B, C, D) from which students were required to either circle or tick one. Each item was scored 2 marks, making a total of 100 marks obtainable. APT was used as a pretest to be sure of the equivalent ability of the students, and it was also used as a posttest after the treatment had been administered to determine the effect of the treatment on the students' academic performances. The instrument was given to two secondary school mathematics teachers and an expert in measurement and evaluation for validation. The test-retest method was used to generate two sets of scores from students outside the sample of this study, and the scores were correlated using the PPMC to determine their internal consistency. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.92.

Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher carried out the data collection procedure in stages for four weeks. The researcher visited the selected schools for permission to use the students and some of the school facilities, as well as to discuss the best possible way to administer the treatment with mathematics teachers who were the research assistants. This was followed by the establishment of the readiness assurance to determine the digital level of the students. The readiness lasted for two weeks, during which time students were onboarded to the various learning platforms. Afterwards, the Algebra Performance Test (APT) was administered as a pretest to the two experimental groups and the control group to ascertain their equivalence in ability. In the second stage, the experimental groups were taught using the Gamified Quizizz and Google Classroom Platforms, taking cognisance of the students' previous knowledge on the concepts of Simplification of Algebraic Expressions, Simple Equations and Variations. The students were actively engaged and were encouraged to interact with each other on the platforms, while the control groups were also taught the same concepts using the conventional face-to-face method. Thereafter, treatments commenced and lasted for four weeks of twelve periods. At the end of the treatments, the items from the instruments were reorganised and re-administered to the same students. The scores obtained from the second administration of the instrument served as the post-test scores in this study. The reason for the reorganisation was to distract the students from realising that the questions were the same. The test items were the same for both experimental groups and the control groups. The pre-test scores were compared to find out if both experimental and control groups were equivalent before exposure to treatment. The post-test achievement scores were compared with pre-test achievement scores to determine the effects of treatments. The post-test was scored and used to generate quantitative data, which was analysed using descriptive statistics of Means and Standard deviation to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One: What difference exists among students taught using Gamified Quizizz Platform (GQP), Google Classroom Platform (GCP) and Face-to-Face Method (FFM) in their academic performance in Algebra concepts?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the difference that exists among students taught using Gamified Quizizz Platform (GQP), Google Classroom Platform (GCP) and Face-to-Face Method (FFM) in their academic performance in Algebra concepts

Instructional Strategy	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
GQP	83	44.18	12.10	65.92	10.71	21.74
GCP	86	45.20	10.08	57.94	9.92	12.74
FFM	82	45.49	10.88	46.48	10.42	0.99

The result of Table 1 showed the difference that exists among students taught using GQP, GCP and FFM in their academic performance in Algebra concepts. The result revealed that the performance of the students taught Algebra concepts using GQP was higher (Pretest: Mean = 44.18, SD = 12.10, Posttest: Mean = 65.92, SD = 10.71, Mean Gain = 21.74) than students taught Algebra concepts using GCP (Pretest: Mean = 45.20, SD = 10.08, Posttest: Mean = 57.94, SD = 9.92, Mean Gain = 12.74), and followed by students taught Algebra concepts using FFM (Pretest: Mean = 45.49, SD = 10.88, Posttest: Mean = 46.48, SD = 10.42, Mean Gain = 0.99). The difference in the mean gain showed that students taught Algebra concepts using GQP performed better than their counterparts taught using GCP, and followed by the students taught using the FFM.

Research Question Two: What difference exists between the academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts?

Table 2: Mean score and standard deviation of the academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts

Gender	n	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Male	138	43.21	11.11	58.04	13.06	14.83
Female	113	47.09	10.55	55.36	12.85	8.27

Table 2 shows the difference that exists between the academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts. The result revealed that the performance level of the male students taught Algebra concepts was higher (Pretest: Mean = 43.21, SD = 11.11, Posttest: Mean = 58.04, SD = 13.06, Mean Gain = 14.83) than their female counterparts (Pretest: Mean = 47.09, SD = 10.55, Posttest: Mean = 55.36, SD = 12.85, Mean Gain = 8.27). The difference in the mean gain academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts differs substantially in favour of the male students.

Research Question Three: What is the joint effect of learning platform (GQP, GCP and FFM) and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts?

Table 3: Mean score and standard deviation of the joint effect of Gamified Quizizz Platform (GQP), Google Classroom Platform (GCP) and Face-to-Face Method (FFM) and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts

Instructional Strategy	Gender	n	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
			\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
GQP	Male	50	44.20	12.53	65.86	10.66	21.66
	Female	33	44.15	11.60	66.00	10.94	21.85
GCP	Male	46	42.46	8.66	58.78	11.16	16.32
	Female	40	48.35	10.77	56.97	8.29	8.62
FFM	Male	42	42.86	11.85	47.90	10.80	5.04
	Female	40	48.25	9.12	44.98	9.92	-3.27

Table 3 showed the joint effect of GQP, GCP and FFM and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts. The result revealed that the performance of the female students taught Algebra concepts using GQP was slightly higher (Pretest: mean = 44.15, SD = 11.60, Posttest: Mean = 66.00, SD = 10.94, Mean Gain = 21.85) than their male counterparts (Pretest: mean = 44.20, SD = 12.53, Posttest: 65.86, SD = 10.66, Mean Gain = 21.66).

The result also revealed that the performance of the male students taught Algebra concepts using GCP was higher (Pretest: mean = 42.46, SD = 8.66, Posttest: 58.78, SD = 11.16, Mean Gain = 16.32) than their female counterparts (Pretest: mean = 48.35, SD = 10.77, Posttest: 56.97, SD = 8.29, Mean Gain = 8.62).

The result also revealed that the performance of the male students taught Algebra concepts using FFM was higher (Pretest: mean = 42.86, SD = 11.85, Posttest: 47.90, SD = 10.80, Mean Gain = 5.04) than their female counterparts (Pretest: mean = 48.25, SD = 9.12, Posttest: 44.98, SD = 9.92, Mean Gain = -3.27).

Consequently, the joint effect of GQP, GCP and FFM and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts differs to some level. The difference in the mean gain showed that female students taught Algebra concepts using GQP slightly performed better than their male counterparts. Also, male students taught using GCP performed better than their female counterparts. Lastly, male students taught using FFM performed better than their female counterparts.

Hypothesis One: No significant difference exists among students taught using GQP, those taught using GCP and those taught using FFM in their academic performance in Algebra concepts.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA on the difference exists among students taught using GQP, those taught using GCP and those taught using FFM in their academic performance in Algebra concepts

Dependent Variable: Posttest

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	16320.18 ^a	3	5440.06	51.71	0.00	0.39
Intercept	55945.63	1	55945.63	531.80	0.00	0.68
Pretest	570.78	1	570.78	5.43	0.02	0.02
Group	15439.31	2	7719.65	73.38	0.00	0.37
Error	25984.79	247	105.20			
Total	853023.00	251				
Corrected Total	42304.97	250				

a. R Squared = .386 (Adjusted R Squared = .378)

Table 4 shows that a significant difference exists among students taught using GQP, those taught using GCP and those taught using FFM in their academic performance in Algebra concepts ($F_2 = 73.38$, $df = 247$, $P < 0.05$). Hence, null hypothesis two was rejected at the 0.05 alpha level. The partial eta squared value of 0.37 indicates a small effect size, demonstrating that the difference in the means slightly differed across the groups. This indicates that a significant difference exists among students taught using Gamified Quizizz Platform, those taught using Google Classroom Platform and those taught using Face-to-Face Method in their academic performance in Algebra concepts.

Hypothesis Two: No significant difference exists between the academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts.

Table 5: Summary of ANCOVA on the difference that exists between the academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts.

Dependent Variable: Posttest

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	1140.43 ^a	2	570.21	3.44	0.03	0.03
Intercept	55178.75	1	55178.75	332.43	0.00	0.57
Pretest	696.40	1	696.40	4.20	0.04	0.02
Gender	259.55	1	259.55	1.56	0.21	0.01
Error	41164.54	248	165.99			
Total	853023.00	251				
Corrected Total	42304.97	250				

a. R Squared = .027 (Adjusted R Squared = .019)

Table 5 shows that there is no significant difference exists between the academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts ($F_1 = 1.56$, $df = 248$, $P > 0.05$). Hence, null hypothesis five was retained at the 0.05 alpha level, indicating that there is no significant difference exists between the academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts. The partial eta squared value of 0.01 indicates a small effect size, demonstrating that the difference in the means does not substantially differ across the groups.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant joint effect of learning platform and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts.

Table 6: Summary of ANCOVA on the joint effect of learning platforms (GQP, GCP and FFM) and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts

Dependent Variable: Posttest

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	16444.67 ^a	6	2740.78	25.86	0.00	0.39
Intercept	52359.68	1	52359.68	494.03	0.00	0.67
Pretest	449.11	1	449.11	4.24	0.04	0.02
Group	15229.15	2	7614.58	71.85	0.00	0.37
Gender	68.00	1	68.00	0.64	0.42	0.00
Group * Gender	57.11	2	28.56	0.27	0.76	0.00
Error	25860.31	244	105.99			
Total	853023.00	251				
Corrected Total	42304.97	250				

a. R Squared = .389 (Adjusted R Squared = .374)

Table 6 shows that there is no significant joint effect of learning platform (GQP, GCP and FFM) and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts ($F_2 = 0.27$, $df = 244$, $P > 0.05$). Hence, null hypothesis eight was retained at the 0.05 alpha level, indicating that there was no significant joint effect of learning platform and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts. The partial eta squared value of 0.00 indicates a

small effect size, demonstrating that the difference in the means does not differ across the groups.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question one showed that the performance of the students taught Algebra concepts using GQP was higher than students taught Algebra concepts using GCP, and followed by students taught Algebra concepts using FFM. The difference in the mean gain showed that students taught Algebra concepts using GQP performed better than their counterparts taught using GCP, and followed by the students taught using the FFM. Furthermore, the result of hypothesis one showed that a significant difference exists among students taught using GQP, those taught using GCP and those taught using FFM in their academic performance in Algebra concepts. This finding is in line with Naseem's (2021) study which found a significant effect of Quizizz platform on the performance of grade VII Mathematics students. The significant outcome for anxiety in Mathematics was also found when the overall effect was measured. This finding is further supported by Alex and Olawumi (2021), whose study revealed that the use of mathematical games has a significant positive effect on the academic performance of students in Mathematics; the use of mathematical games was beneficial to students irrespective of their gender and scoring ability. This finding is further corroborated by the findings of Attah, Ogunlade and Falade (2024) that the adoption of the gamification element has an impact on junior-senior high school students' mathematics performance. This result is also consistent with that of Landers (2014), Langendahl et al (2016), and Smiderle et al (2020), who revealed a positive effect of gamification elements on students' learning outcomes.

The result of research question two showed that the performance level of the male students taught Algebra concepts was higher than their female counterparts. The difference in the mean gain academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts differs substantially in favour of the male students. Furthermore, the result of hypothesis two showed that there is no significant difference exists between the academic performance of male and female students in Algebra concepts. The findings of this study do not support those of Ajayi and Imoko (2015) who examined gender inequalities in mathematics achievement and retention. The study showed that achievement and retention scores between male and female students who were taught algebra via PBL did not significantly differ, demonstrating that both sexes are capable of competing and cooperating in mathematics. The study is also not consistent with Rodríguez et al. (2019), who in their study found that boys generally showed higher motivation and more positive attitudes towards mathematics compared to girls.

The result of the research question three showed the joint effect of GQP, GCP and FFM and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts. The result revealed that female students taught Algebra concepts using GQP slightly performed better than their male counterparts. Also, male students taught using GCP performed better than their female counterparts. Lastly, male students taught using FFM performed better than their female counterparts. Furthermore, the result of hypothesis three showed that there is no significant joint effect of GQP, GCP, FFM and gender on students' academic performance in Algebra concepts. This finding is in line with Oliveira et al. (2023), whose study compared students using a gamified version of an educational system to those using a non-gamified version, showing higher performance in the gamified group. This finding is also supported by Gupta & Pathania (2020), who found that students using Google Classroom had better access to learning materials, could communicate more effectively with peers, and showed improved academic performance.

Conclusion

The study found that students taught Algebra using the Gamified Quizizz Platform (GQP) performed significantly better than those taught with Gamified Classroom Practice (GCP) and Face-to-Face Method (FFM). While male students showed higher mean scores than females, the difference was not statistically significant. Gender did not significantly influence performance across methods, though GQP slightly favoured female students. Overall, gamified approaches, especially GQP, proved effective in enhancing Algebra performance, supporting prior research on the benefits of gamification in mathematics education.

Recommendations

Based on the results obtained from this study, the following recommendations are then put forward;

1. Mathematics teachers should adopt gamified teaching strategies using platforms such as Quizizz to improve academic performance in Algebra concepts.
2. Teacher training institutions should provide pre-service and in-service training programs on gamified teaching methods and digital learning platforms, enabling teachers to create engaging and effective learning experiences for all students.
3. Technology providers should collaborate with schools in Rivers State to develop and provide affordable, user-friendly gamified platforms like Quizizz (GQP) tailored to the needs of secondary school students and teachers, ensuring widespread accessibility.

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